

Project Crisanto: A Business Imperative for Local Government Units

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Abstract:- This descriptive-evaluative research determined the satisfaction of residents and the acceptability level of the designed project charter.

Specifically, the study answered the following: 1) Constituent's level of satisfaction of different income-generating services of the barangays along with efficiency and quality of service; 2) Project charter that boosts the income-generating services of the barangay through its level of acceptability in terms of usability, profitability, and social responsibility.

The respondents were the thirty-six (36) residents as well as selected constituents from Barangay I, Barangay III, Barangay Cobangbang, Barangay Mambalite, and Barangay Camambugan. The researcher focused on the data collected during the design phase of the project charter. The proposal was presented to the thirty-eight (38) faculty of Camarines Norte State College, the College of Business and Public Administration to determine if the project was beneficial and promote income to the community.

The significant findings were: 1) Generally, respondents perceived satisfaction level in terms of efficiency had an overall weighted mean of 1.93, interpreted as satisfactory. The results have shown that maximizing their resources in creating projects has the lowest weighted average of 1.64; 2) Observed practices on quality of service had an overall average weighted mean of 1.66, interpreted as seldom observed. According to the statistical data, the lowest in the rank was the usefulness of implementation with a weighted mean of 1.49 concluded an understanding that has never been observed; 3) As for usability, the project got an average weighted mean of 2.69. The respondents recognized the Project CRISANTO could help minimize specific issues or problems, address some of the barangay's concerns, and discuss some difficulties; 4) In terms of profitability, the project could generate income and get the average weighted mean of 2.80, interpreted as highly acceptable. This implies that the respondents recognized the Project CRISANTO could give additional revenue and be a source of income for the additional fund's barangay; 5) In terms of social responsibility, the project got an average weighted mean of 2.87, interpreted as highly acceptable.

The conclusions were: 1) Residents of the barangays were satisfied in terms of efficiency; 2) Service quality of the barangay was seldom observed; 3) the designed project CRISANTO in terms of usability was highly acceptable; 4) the profitability level of the project was highly acceptable; and, 5) the social responsibility of the project was also highly acceptable.

Keywords:- Satisfaction, Acceptability, Income Generating Projects, Local Government Unit, Camarines Norte.

I. INTRODUCTION

Barangay was the smallest political unit in the Philippines. Each municipality or city was made up of barangays. The barangay government unit comprises elected officials called the Punong Barangay, the chief executive, the Sangguniang Barangay members, Kagawads, and the Sangguniang Kabataan Chairman. The appointed officials were the barangay Secretary, the barangay Treasurer, the members of the Lupong Tagapamayapa, and the barangay tanods.

The 1991 Local Government Code of Republic Act No. 7160, Chapter 1 Section 440 defines the role of the municipality as "consisting of a group of barangays to serve primarily as a general-purpose government for the coordination and delivery of essential regular and direct services and effective governance of the inhabitants within the territorial jurisdiction and the municipal mayor heads this.

According to the Philippines Local Government Code, Book III, Section 384, Barangay, as the basic political unit, acts as the primary entity for the preparation and execution of government policies, strategies, services, initiatives, and community events, and as a forum where people's collective views could be articulated, crystallized and considered and where disagreements could be pleasant. Section 391 of the Local Government Code of the Philippines, Powers, Duties, and Functions, The Sangguniang Barangay shall Hold fundraising activities for Barangay projects without the need to secure permits from any national or local office or agency. The proceeds from such activities shall be tax-exempt and shall accrue to the general fund of the Barangay: Provided, That in the appropriation thereof, the specific purpose for which such fundraising activity has been held shall be first satisfied: Provided, further, That no fundraising activities shall be held within sixty(60) days immediately preceding and after a national or local election, recall, referendum, or plebiscite: lastly, fundraising activities should comply with federal policy standards and regulations

on morals, health, and safety of the persons participating therein.

The researcher proposed an income-generating project that could help the barangays and the entire community of Daet, Camarines Norte. The proposed project would create an income and serve as an additional fund that would help aid the problems and issues of the barangays in Daet, Camarines Norte. The researcher believes that the result of this study would benefit the following: Client. Having an income-generating project, the barangays would provide lots of assistance that enable them to help their constituents; Barangay Official. This study would help the Barangay workers improve their productivity and create strategies to improve their clients' services. Also, they would be able to change their negative feedback into positive; Researcher. The research would help them understand the importance of the public or customer relation to an institution or business sectors and understand why the barangay gives an enormous contribution to the economy; Future Researchers. This may be additional data and source of information on their related studies and field of interest to cover the insufficiency of literature and reviews related to income-generating projects and client's satisfaction. Likewise, it may serve as a check on their studies' significant findings using different principles and validity analysis.

A. Theoretical Framework

This has become the structure that could enable or support the research study. Furthermore, the theoretical framework introduces and describes the concept, which helps to explain why there is a study area under investigation.

Figure 1 demonstrates the relationships between the theories and concepts that contributed to the development of the analysis.

The Marxist Theory (Trainer, 2010) on capitalism is about the society of primitive, slave feudal, and capitalist. In a capitalist society, capitalists own and control productive resources (i.e., capital). Workers own only their labor and work for capitalists, who then own the product and sell it for a profit. The capital, machinery, mines, factories, among others, were the vital productive factors. These were owned and controlled by capitalists as distinct from being owned by all society members, which is the focal idea in socialism varieties.

Relative to the study, this theory could help to understand better how the program would be executed, especially how the project would start since capital was the most crucial factor in project development.

Therefore, project management (PM) should also consider the System's Theory whenever operating at full capacity such an entire organization (Laszlo and Krippner, 2013). System theories take a holistic view of the organization's specific function, including how the different parts of the organization communicate effectively and its impact on human ethical conduct. When certainly compared with the study, an efficient and productive project is more likely to succeed.

Taylor's (2013) Theory creates four principles of scientific management. These were 1) time and motion study which deals with the way jobs were performed and find new ways to do them; 2) teach, train and develop the workman with improved methods of doing work; 3) interest of employer and employees should be fully harmonized to secure mutually understanding relations between them, and 4) establish appropriate levels of performance and pay a premium for higher performance. These principles were aimed at improving economic efficiency, especially labor productivity (2013).

As to the concept of Taylor's theory, it would help maximize the project's potentiality, particularly when it comes to resources and how to strategize the initiative properly. Implementation of a project that was below expectations leads to dissatisfied citizens. In contrast, a performance that meets expectations produces community client satisfaction. When the citizens in the barangay are satisfied, they are more inclined to take part in different community projects

Fayol's Theory (2013) is known for its 14 principles of management, and these principles could be applied for IGP operations. For IGP, work division was crucial because it would focus familiarity and expertise on a particular job assignment. The IGP in-charge should be given an opportunity in line with his responsibility. IGP personnel should instill discipline in the system. IGP goals and objectives, which aim to increase its income, were geared towards the total barangay target hence the unity of direction. Unity of command was also followed by IGP personnel. Subordination of individual interest to the general welfare was imperative because there were projects that IGP personnel may have direct access to monetary transactions or collection, thus the need for IGP personnel to possess high integrity and honesty.

When particularly compared to the study, In order to motivate the participants in the project and constituents to partake in the actual operation of IGP actively, proper remuneration of the project managers assigned, along with the constituents' laborers who contribute to the productivity of the particular project, should be well compensated. Nevertheless, Team member motivation was a personal response mostly to the experience gained.

Fig. 1: Theoretical Paradigm

B. Conceptual Framework

Figure 2 presents the conceptual paradigm of the study.

The satisfaction level was measured in terms of efficiency and quality of service, which was how effective the barangay project was and how well the residents were pleased with the barangay's service.

The acceptability level focused on the usability, profitability, and social responsibility of the designed income-generating project. The project was evaluated based on the data obtained and its appropriateness in providing revenue sources to the barangay.

In this research, the output refers to Project CRISANTO. This project charter could boost the Barangays' income-generating services in Daet, Camarines Norte, and benefit the citizens and the barangays' whole community.

Thus, merely having such a research project that is also a pretty good investment can indeed help enough to provide a quality service. Similarly, word-of-mouth, personal needs, previous experiences, and public relations ascertain the needs and expectations of the citizen. These factors are relevant to their experience, and this is a comparison of expectations and perceptions that provides a measure of the residents' satisfaction.

Fig. 2: Conceptual Framework

C. Objectives of the Study

This study determined the constituent's satisfaction and came up with an income-generating project for the barangays in Daet, Camarines Norte, based on the following; (1) Determine the constituent's level of satisfaction of different income-generating services of the barangays along: (a) efficiency (b) quality of service (2) Design a project charter that could boost the income-generating services of the barangay and determine its level of acceptability in terms of (a) usability (b) profitability, (c) social responsibility.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study used the descriptive design to determine the satisfaction level of the residents in terms of efficiency and quality of service to be able to design a project charter that could boost the income-generating services of the barangay by determining its level of acceptability in terms of usability, profitability, and social responsibility. The researcher collected data in order to describe the nature of the situation and to answer questions. The measurement and description of the variables were carried out quantitatively.

B. Respondents' Profile

This study's respondents were the thirty-six (36) residents as well as selected constituents from Barangay I, Barangay III, Barangay Cobangbang, Barangay Mambalite, and Barangay Camambugan due to COVID-19 pandemic and constrained barangays. The thirty-eight (38) faculty members of Camarines Norte State College, College of Business and Public Administration were respondents in examining the Project CRISANTO. Therefore, purposive and total enumeration sampling.

The researcher focused on the data collected during the design phase of the project necessary for this study. The project was presented to the thirty-eight (38) faculty of the Camarines Norte State College, the College of Business and Public Administration to determine whether the project was beneficial to the community or help promote barangay-revenue as their income-generating project.

C. Instrumentation

The researcher focused on the data collected during the design phase of the project necessary for this study. The project was presented to the thirty-eight (38) faculty of the Camarines Norte State College, the College of Business and Public Administration to determine whether the project was beneficial to the community or help promote barangay-revenue as their income-generating project.

D. Data Collection Materials and Techniques

The researcher provided questionnaires to the thirty-six (36) respondents from the barangay residents in Daet, Camarines Norte, and thirty-eight (38) respondents from Camarines Norte State College, College of Business and Public Administration. It was the primary research tool used to determine barangay satisfaction and the income-generating project acceptability level. The survey was segmented into various sections. The first was respondents' perception of how they rate the barangay's efficiency and quality of service. The second was perceptions in terms of participatory governance, maximizing resources, income-generating projects, the usefulness of implementation, benefits to the constituents, and the summary of observed practices on service quality. The third was acceptability level along with usability, profitability, and social responsibility that was being presented to Camarines Norte State College, College of Business and Public Administration, determining the level of acceptability of the Project C.R.I.S.A.N.T.O. (Convert and Reduce Plastic with Income Sustainability by Applying New Technology to Obtain Waste Minimization).

The secondary data of this study were collected from books, published thesis, and internet websites. A questionnaire was also be used to gather primary data. The researcher submitted the questionnaire to his adviser to check, enhance, and provide suggestions and recommendations.

E. Data Analysis Techniques

Documentary analysis and informal interviews determined the constituents' level of satisfaction and basis for designing the project charter. The rating scale was used for the challenges encountered in its implementation.

For the determination and interpretation of data collected, the following statistical tools were used: (1) frequency count, mean, and ranks organized the data, profile of the respondents. (2) weighted mean determined the level of satisfaction and acceptability of the IGP, as well as the timeliness and quality of service.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Satisfaction Level

Efficiency. The respondents' perceived satisfaction level in terms of efficiency and timeliness was presented in Table 1. The barangay accepts their constituents' suggestions in creating projects that got the highest weighted mean, 2.19, with a corresponding rating of satisfactory. This was followed by addressing their concerns in creating projects, 2.11, satisfactory; third in rank was the constituents highly encouraged to support and participate in the barangay's project, got 1.92, interpreted as satisfactory; fourth was constituents have benefited from the project of the barangay, got 1.78, interpreted as satisfactory; The least was the barangay maximizing their resources in creating projects, got 1.64, interpreted as satisfactory.

Parameters	W.M.	Int
1. The constituents are highly encouraged to support and participate in the barangay's project	1.92	S
2. Constituents have benefited from the project of the barangay	1.78	S
3. The barangay is maximizing its resources in creating projects	1.64	S
4. The barangay is addressing their concerns in creating projects	2.11	S
5. The barangay is accepting the suggestions of their constituents in creating projects	2.19	S
Average Weighted Mean	1.93	S

Table 1: Respondents' Perceived Satisfactionlevel In Terms Of Efficiency

Legend:

2.36 – 3.00 Outstanding (O)

1.68 – 2.35 Satisfactory (S)

1.00 – 1.67 Poor (P)

W.M.- Weighted Mean

Int - Interpretation

Generally, respondents perceived satisfaction level in terms of efficiency had an overall weighted mean of 1.93, interpreted as satisfactory. The results show that maximizing their resources in creating projects has the lowest weighted average of 1.64, interpreted as satisfactory, which implies that they do not make fair use of their resources in planning and constructing projects. All resources must be listed explicitly so that they probably know how to optimize their resources significantly—having a study on an implementation of a project would maximize the use of resources and chance to make it successful. This includes understanding the issues of the barangay that need to be resolved and what the community needs. The barangay must reassess the available resources and have adequately researched the concept to see if it would really benefit the community or only a few would be benefited from it.

Miranda (2016) stated that the management of the IGP should explore the possibilities of establishing useful links with other institutions for accessing funds, innovating

technology, developing, traveling, and, more specifically, obtaining accreditation or having a membership at local and even national levels in some different trade organizations or market development councils. Local governments, such as the Barangay Unit, should help make the most use of the allocation fund to establish a system that would help their residential neighborhoods.

Quality of Service. Table 2 shows the observed practices on quality of service. Maximizing resources got the highest weighted mean of 1.65 interpreted as seldom observed; followed by Participatory Governance, 1.58 interpreted as seldom observed; Benefits to the constituents, 1.57 interpreted as seldom observed; Income generating projects, 1.52 interpreted as seldom observed; and the least was The Usefulness of implementation, 1.49 interpreted as never observed. The average weighted average for observed practices on quality of service got 1.66, interpreted as seldom observed.

PARAMETERS	BARANGAY					Overall Weighted Mean	Int	Rank
	Cobangbang (n=8)	Mambalite (n=7)	I (n=8)	Camambugan (n=7)	III (n=6)			
	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean	Mean			
Participatory Governance	1.50	1.60	.55	1.60	1.70	1.58	SO	2
Maximizing resources	1.68	1.54	.65	1.54	1.87	1.65	SO	1
Income-generating projects	1.53	1.71	.45	1.51	1.40	1.52	SO	4
Usefulness of implementation	1.28	1.29	.40	2.06	1.47	1.49	N	5
Benefits to the constituents	1.73	1.31	.58	1.66	1.57	1.57	SO	3
Overall Mean	1.65	1.60	.63	1.76	1.70	1.66	SO	

Table 2: Observed Practices On Quality Of Service

LEGEND

INTERVAL INTERPRETATION (Int)

3.50 – 4.00 Always Observed (A)

2.50 – 3.49 Sometimes Observed (S)

1.50 – 2.49 Seldom Observed (SO)

1.00 – 1.49 Never Observed (N)

Observed practices on quality of service had an overall average weighted mean of 1.66, interpreted as seldom observed. On the basis of the data obtained, the lowest in the rank was the usefulness of implementation with a weighted mean of 1.49 with an understanding that has never been observed.

Indeed, local governments could support their residents by distributing finances and putting a plan into motion that helps the community. However, barangay should carry out an analysis and study to create, implement, and utilize its resources to set up new initiatives relevant to barangay and use its fund effectively to meet its constituents' needs.

Barangay must consider its members' interests to ensure that the programs and services to be implemented were useful and essential to their extent. There was a strong need for an effort to set up services that were associated with the advancement of barangay and its constituents. When a project does not meet the needs of the people of the barangay, it is not an effective project.

Kotelnikov (2012) pointed out that satisfied clients deepen their relationship with the company. When the client was satisfied with the total quality of service, they tend to meet the client's expectations. In the context of this study, the relationship between barangay and residents or both parties would be more uncomplicated if the local constituency or Barangay residents were satisfied. Residents could even support barangay initiatives and programs.

B. Project Design

The project was based on the results obtained from the level of satisfaction of barangay residents and the related literature and studies collected. It was also anchored in the results of the efficiency and quality of the service outcomes.

Project C.R.I.S.A.N.T.O.: A Business Imperative for Local Government Units.

Daet was one of the biggest progressive municipalities in the province of Camarines Norte. It has twenty-five (25) barangays and comprises many commercial buildings and big establishments that were now continuing to grow. However, Barangays in Daet face the biggest problem in terms of garbage disposal, affecting the residents' current lives. The residents' poor discipline in waste management could cause clogging waterways and, eventually, flooding that brings sickness to the community.

This becomes one of the biggest concerns, especially during the rainy season. Dr. Ronaldo Paguirigan, head officer of Municipal Environment and Natural Resource Office (MENRO), reiterated that the Solid Waste Management Board (2018) states that 69.69% of recyclable plastic waste was being collected every year. The total plastic waste in Daet, Camarines Norte, has an average of 3,353.42 kilograms per day, 1,224,000.00 kilograms, or 1,224.00 tons per year. This number equates to the biggest problem of the Local Government Unit of Daet: how could they manage the massive amount of plastic waste?

The proponent came up with this proposal because of the stated main problem of Daet, Camarines Norte, in solid waste, specifically the plastic waste of every resident in every barangays and business establishments. This project aims to aid the dilated issues of trash that were becoming difficult to deal with.

The specific objectives of Project CRISANTO (Convert and Reduce Plastic with Income Sustainability by Applying New Technology to Obtain Waste Minimization) were to help every barangay to generate income through collecting plastic waste and convert it to a tile with the use of a machine called plastic melter, and a molder. Hence, it could help lessen the plastic waste from the establishments and barangay residents in Daet, Camarines Norte. This could prevent floods, sickness, and harmful effects on the health of the residents in Daet.

➤ *Economic Situation:*

The main sources of earning a living of the residents in the barangays of Daet, Camarines Norte were by having their owned sari-sari stores, some of them were members of 4P's (Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program), and others way of earning money was through Fish Vending, Taho, Siopao, Cassava Making, Tricycle Operator, and the majority of them were Government and Private Employees working in the Centro of Daet, Camarines Norte.

➤ *Project Stakeholders / Partner Organizations:*

- LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT (LGU) DAET
- MUNICIPAL ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE (MENRO)
- PROVINCIAL ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES OFFICE (PENRO)
- DEPARTMENT OF ENVIRONMENT & NATURAL RESOURCES (DENR)
- CAMARINES NORTE STATE COLLEGE – CBPA DEPARTMENT
- DEPARTMENT OF TRADE AND INDUSTRY (DTI)
- 4P's (Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program)
- THE 25 BARANGAYS OF DAET, CAMARINES NORTE
- PASOA ORGANIZATION – CNSC Chapter
- DEPARTMENT OF INTERIOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT
- SM HYPERMART
- DEPARTMENT OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- National Food Authority
- JCI BULAWAN
- Rotaract Club of Daet.

➤ *Beneficiaries:*

The project would benefit the 25 Barangays, LGU-Daet, and the entire community of Daet, Camarines Norte.

IV. GOALS AND OBJECTIVES

The project's key objective was to propose an Income Generation Program for the Barangays of Daet, Camarines Norte, and reduce plastic waste's growing issue.

The C.R.I.S.A.N.T.O. Project aims to:

- Generate an income for the Barangays of Daet, Camarines Norte, through plastic waste production.
- Find alternative ways to minimize their garbage into useful thing/s that could help maintain the barangay's cleanliness.
- Provide financial assistance out of the generated income to procure the barangay needs and financing barangay activities/programs.
- Promote community interests through this project.

V. PROJECT DETAILS

A. Implementation Mechanics

This project's proponent would harmonize and present this program to the LGU-Daet to evaluate Project C.R.I.S.A.N.T.O Proposal. The Local Government Unit of Daet would create a cooperative and a Board of Management (BOM) to run this project. LGU-Daet would also coordinate with the DENR, DILG, DOST for the assistance of the resource speaker and implementation of the program. The LGU-Daet would communicate with MENRO to conduct a seminar with Dr. Ronaldo Paguirigan, chief officer of MENRO, who would discuss the proper segregation of the garbage, and Engineer Ricky Eboña, the supplier of the machine, to educate the officials and members on how to manage and operate the said machine. Since it collaborates with different organizations, any cost incurred would be shouldered by LGU-Daet and its partners. In order to lessen the burden of the capital needed, the LGU-Daet would tap into government agencies that were willing to extend their help in this program.

B. Manpower Requirements

Since it was an income-generating program and shared responsibility for the community of every barangays in Daet, the barangay officials and the assistance of different organizations were vital for the said scheme's operations. Also, the LGU-Daet would form an organization/cooperative to manage and run the said IGP. The barangay Officials could also ask for assistance from the 4P's members and unemployed residents to cooperate in this project.

C. Monitoring & Evaluation

To ensure sustainability and productivity, the LGU-Daet would be conducting a scheduled visitation to the site. For the community, the barangay officials would also ensure the proper care operation. The assistance of the DILG, DTI, MENRO, DENR, and PENRO was also essential to safeguard the project's sustainability and efficiency.

D. Deliverables

Since this project's beneficiaries were the barangays in Daet, Camarines Norte, they could have twenty percent (20%) of the Project CRISANTO's overall net profit. The community of Daet could also be helped by eliminating and minimizing the plastic wastes and avoiding diseases since one of the main problems of the town of Daet was waste disposal. Equipment and new technology were also one of the main deliverables in this project. Similarly, the environment could be benefited from the project by eradicating the harmful effect of plastic waste on our nature and natural habitat.

E. Project Risks

➤ Internal

- Lack of communication.
- Participants became disengaged from the project. Executive management disregards project communications and meetings.
- Executives fail to support the project. The project team may lack the ability to achieve the objectives of the project. In such cases, support for executive management was essential to the success of the project. If this does not materialize, the project fails.
- The project team misunderstands the requirements. When the project team misinterprets requirements, a gap develops between expectations, requirements, and work packages.
- Low team motivation.

➤ External

- Uncontrolled changes and continuous growth.
- Disruptions such as acts of nature.
- Legal and regulatory change

F. Budget Proposal

All materials needed for the recycled plastic waste production would be shouldered by the LGU-Daet, DILG, and its partner's organization in any incurred expenses to materialize the production. The initial cash needed for the implementation and operation of Project CRISANTO in Year 1 was P532,420, with a total cost of P1,766,496 for the whole project duration. The proposal would require two (2) plastic melter machines with a total operating capacity of 24,000 tiles that needs 1,600 Liters of coconut oil and two machine operators for its annual production. Cost-Benefit Analysis shows that the project would generate a discounted net cash flow of P685,753 and has a cost-benefit ratio of 1.41, which shows that the project's benefit was higher than its cost. After computing the return on investment of the project, it shows a good gain of 43% over its cost to be incurred.

In this proposal, it considered three financial assumptions. There would be an annual increase of 5% in selling price, 3% direct labor, and 1% increase in direct materials and other costs.

VI. ADVERTISING AND PROMOTION

The main advertising strategy of the project would be through word of mouth communication. The project would produce high-quality tiles at a reasonable cost. Social media advertising and marketing would be used to advertise the product. Additionally, the business would be centered around the quality of the produced product as well as the consumers' budget. All of these initiatives would primarily be used to promote the barangay and expand its services. The partnership with other agencies and organizations was vitally important for the success of the project.

VII. IMPORTANCE OF THE PROJECT

A. The Benefits of Plastic Production

- Discipline household member to segregate their waste
- Reduce the plastic waste of the community
- Flood prevention
- Prevent illness
- Income generation /could be the barangay's other source of income
- Job opportunity for unemployed residents
- Attracts green and ethical investment
- Raises awareness within its community relative to social responsibility

B. Advantages of Diverting Plastic Waste

- Reduce plastic waste
- Convert plastic waste into reusable material that could be used for making various products.
- Recycling and repurposing plastic waste could save the environment and people from being affected by this plastic waste.

C. The help of Diverting Plastic Waste

- Reduce plastic waste that causes clogging waterways and floods
- Prevent harmful effect on the residents
- Reduce pollution

D. Acceptability level

Usability. The respondents' perceived acceptability level in terms of usability was presented in Table 3. Usability refers to how defined consumers may use a product or service to meet the targets set with usefulness, availability, and satisfaction in a given context of use. It was often referred to as a strategy for enhancing the ease of use during the development process.

The project could minimize the specific issues or problems, getting the highest weighted mean of 2.92 with a highly acceptable corresponding rating. The project was useful and beneficial, 2.87, highly acceptable, and the least was the project maximizing resources, 2.29, acceptable. Generally, respondents perceived acceptability in terms of usability had an overall weighted mean of 2.69, interpreted as highly acceptable.

Parameters	W.M.	Int
1. The project can help to minimize certain issues or problem	2.92	H
2. The project is useful and beneficial	2.87	H
3. The project is maximizing resources	2.29	A
Average Weighted Mean	2.69	H

Table 3: Respondents' Perceived Acceptability Level In Terms Of Usability

Legend:

- 2.36 – 3.00 Highly acceptable (H)
- 1.68 – 2.35 Acceptable (A)
- 1.00 – 1.67 Not acceptable(N)

W.M.- Weighted Mean

Int - Interpretation

The data indicated that the project's usability got an average weighted mean of 2.69. The respondents recognized the Project CRISANTO could help minimize specific issues or problems, address some of the barangay's concerns, and discuss some difficulties. The perceptions of the respondents regarding the project in terms of usability were highly acceptable. To minimize the plastic waste that was becoming difficult to cope with, it could use a feasible approach.

Nevertheless, innovation, collaboration, cooperation with other agencies and organizations, and the creation of partnerships, including involvement in training sessions and conferences, would help improve the project's funding and execution to enhance the revenue-generating services of the

barangay. Moreover, effective project management allows organizations to succeed in business.

Cuadrado (2016) There should be an implementation of livelihood projects/programs to counter the residents' needs; the institution shall also conduct outreach programs such as barangay clean-up and tree planting activities to develop a better relationship between the school and the community. This study would help create programs that would promote and escalate information that emphasizes the other community resources to produce more livelihood projects.

Profitability. The respondents' perceived acceptability level in terms of profitability was presented in Table 4. This could be described as a benefit left over from the sales that a project earns after it has incurred all the expenses. The project could generate income that got the highest weighted mean of 2.84 with a highly acceptable corresponding rating. The project could be the barangay's other source of income,

2.79, highly acceptable, and the least was the project's return on investment, 2.76, highly acceptable. Generally, respondents who perceived acceptability in terms of profitability had an overall weighted mean of 2.80, interpreted as highly acceptable. Overall weighted mean got 2.80, interpreted as highly acceptable.

Parameters	W.M.	Int
1. The project can generate income	2.84	H
2. The project has a return on investment	2.76	H
3. The project can be the barangay's other source of income	2.79	H
Average Weighted Mean	2.80	H

Table 4: Respondents Perceived Acceptability In Terms Of Profitability

Legend:

- 2.36 – 3.00 Highly acceptable (H)
- 1.68 – 2.35 Acceptable (A)
- 1.00 – 1.67 Not acceptable (N)

W.M. - Weighted Mean
Int - Interpretation

The data showed that the project could generate income and got the average weighted mean of 2.80, interpreted as highly acceptable.

This implies that the respondents recognized the Project CRISANTO could generate additional revenue and be a source of income for the additional fund's barangay. The perceptions of the respondents regarding the project in terms of profitability were suitable. Respondents found that the cost-benefit ratio of the project based on the computation presented was high. The project's net present value was projected to be optimistic since its duration was five years.

Karanja (2014) projects should be in accordance with the latest technology to stabilize the market and business challenges, which inevitably make projects inefficient, in order to be able to provide a viable revenue-generating project. A project has to be innovative and in line with modern times, according to his work. It takes the right time to earn the return on a project's investment.

Social Responsibility. This was referring to ethical responsibility that members of society and organizations have the duty to act for their environment and society as a whole. The respondents' perceived acceptability level in terms of social responsibility was presented in Table 5. Social accountability was taking actions that help the community. Also, Income-generating initiatives were profitable and contributed to the well-being of society and the environment.

The project raises awareness within its community relative to social responsibility got the highest weighted mean of 2.89 with a corresponding rating of highly acceptable. The project attracts green and ethical investment, 2.87, highly acceptable, and the least was the project environmentally friendly, 2.84, highly acceptable. Generally, respondents perceived acceptability in terms of social responsibility had an overall weighted mean of 2.87, interpreted as highly acceptable. Overall weighted mean obtained 2.87, interpreted as highly acceptable.

Parameters	W.M.	Int
1. The project is environmentally friendly	2.84	H
2. The project raises awareness within its community relative to social responsibility	2.89	H
3. The project attracts green and ethical investment	2.87	H
Average Weighted Mean	2.87	H

Table 5: Respondents' Perceived Acceptability In Terms Of Social Responsibility

Legend:

- 2.36 – 3.00 Highly acceptable (H)
- 1.68 – 2.35 Acceptable (A)
- 1.00 – 1.67 Not acceptable (N)

W.M. - Weighted Mean
Int - Interpretation

The data showed that in terms of social responsibility, the project got an over-all average weighted mean of 2.87, interpreted as highly acceptable. This implies that the respondents recognized the Project CRISANTO raises awareness relative to economic growth. Respondents recognize that the project would also help the community with opportunities.

Cuadrado (2016) their study on Socio-Economic Status of Barangay Saguma: Basis for Needs Assessment in Identifying Specific Project for Extension Program, concluded that, based on the priority needs of the barangay and the availability of the resources of Agusan del Sur College, Inc., There should be an implementation of livelihood projects/programs to complement the capability developed among the residents, the institution shall also conduct outreach programs such as barangay clean-up and tree planting activities to build a better relationship between the school and the community. These initiatives foster environmental consciousness among community residents.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the statistical data, the residents of the barangays in Daet, Camarines Norte were satisfied in terms of efficiency. Maximizing resources in creating projects were related to the concept of efficiency. The majority of the respondents concentrated on this principle.

Residents seldom observed their barangay's service quality, which concluded an understanding that the respondents were not relatively convinced with the barangays' services. It was clearly shown that there is something that the respondents were looking for in terms of expectation and about the overall performance of their barangay, particularly having a project that would help the community. It was indicated that most of the respondents wished to see more initiatives from their activities.

The project usability was highly acceptable. Concluding that collaboration with other agencies and organizations helps strengthen, utilize the resources, and increase barangay revenue-generating services.

The profitability of the project was highly acceptable. It was concluded that the respondents' perception of the project was appropriate and necessary. Respondents to the survey noted that the project had a high rate of return gains. The expected earnings of the project were projected to be quite optimistic.

The social responsibility of the project was highly acceptable. It has been well fully revealed that the research project will also.

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